

Notes

Activity Coefficients and Effective Ionic Diameters of some Electrolytes in Aqueous Solutions

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Mean ionic activity coefficients of solutes are calculated from the freezing point depression data, using the Gibbs-Duhem equation¹ (Table 1). Effective ionic diameters of the uni-univalent electrolytes have been computed using the equation suggested by Ghosh²,

$$-\log \gamma = (0.624/a^{1/2}) (C^{1/2} - C_0^{1/2}) \quad (1)$$

where γ is the mean activity coefficient of the electrolyte at 298 K, a the effective ionic diameter (\AA), C the molar concentration of electrolyte and C_0 the concentration at which $\log \gamma = 0$. Plots of $\log \gamma$ vs $C^{1/2}$ for the uni-univalent electrolytes are given in Fig. 1. From the slopes of these plots, values of effective ionic diameter (a) have been calculated (Table 2). The observed ionic diameters of the electrolytes studied are in the order: $\text{KCl} >$

$\text{NH}_4\text{NO}_3 > \text{KNO}_3 > \text{KH}_2\text{PO}_4$. The plots of $\log \gamma$ vs $C^{1/2}$ (Fig. 1) are linear upto 1 molar except for KCl where deviation from linearity was observed

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log \gamma$ vs $C^{1/2}$ for electrolytes: (●) NH_4NO_3 , (Δ) KNO_3 , (\square) KCl and (\circ) KH_2PO_4 .

above 0.4 M. A quantity like the extent of hydration (H) may be defined as: $H = a - a'$, where a' represents the sum of the crystallographic radii of the cation and the anion of the electrolyte. The values of crystallographic radii for the various ions are K^+ , 1.33; NH_4^+ , 1.42; Cl^- , 1.81 and NO_3^- , 1.89 \AA (first three values from Ref. 3, the fourth from Ref. 4). The calculated values of H for the 1:1 electrolytes are also included in Table 2. The values depend both upon the nature of the cation as well as the anion constituting the electrolyte molecule, as obviously they should.

TABLE 1—MEAN IONIC ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF SOME ELECTROLYTES AT 298 K

Molarity	Mean ionic activity coefficient (γ)				
	KNO_3^*	KCl	KH_2PO_4	NH_4NO_3	$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$
0.025	0.847	0.858	0.835	0.855	0.800
0.05	0.794 (0.797)	0.808	0.783	0.804	0.717
0.1	0.739 (0.735)	0.764	0.722	0.748	0.634
0.2	0.665 (0.662)	0.712	0.659	0.686	0.563
0.3	0.621 (0.614)	0.685	0.609	0.641	0.502
0.4	0.579 (0.577)	0.666	0.564	0.603	0.463
0.5	0.547 (0.546)	0.650	0.532	0.579	0.433
0.6	0.524 (0.521)	0.634	0.500	0.562	0.405
0.7	0.503 (0.498)	0.630	0.475	0.546	0.386
0.8	0.479 (0.478)	0.619	0.454	0.530	0.368
0.9	0.458 (0.460)	0.611	0.441	0.518	0.354
1.0	0.445 (0.444)	0.602	0.430	0.505	0.339

*Data in parenthesis from Ref. 1.

TABLE 2—CALCULATED IONIC DIAMETERS (a) ACCORDING TO THE GHOSH THEORY AND EXTENT OF HYDRATION (H) OF SOME UNI-UNIVALENT ELECTROLYTES

Electrolyte	a \AA	H \AA
KNO_3	3.31	0.09
KCl	5.46	2.32
KH_2PO_4	2.80	—
NH_4NO_3	3.92	0.61

References

1. W. J. HAMER and Y. C. WU, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data*, 1972, 1, 1047.
2. B. N. GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 398; 1981, 58, 1040.
3. N. A. LANGE, "Handbook of Chemistry", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1967, p. 122.
4. B. E. CONWAY "Ionic Hydration in Chemistry and Biophysics", Elsevier, New York, 1981, p. 62.